

cascades

Cascading climate risks:
Towards adaptive and
resilient European Societies

Deliverable D3.4: Macro-economic Impact Assessment of Cascading Effects of Climate Change

Description:

Climate change impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability studies tend to confine their attention to impacts and responses within the same geographical region. However, this approach ignores cross-border climate change impacts that occur remotely from the location of their initial impact, and that may severely disrupt societies and livelihoods. In this deliverable (D3.4), we apply an impact assessment of cross-border climate change impacts. We evaluate a set of scenarios established in Deliverable D2.1 (Carter et al., 2020) based on the widely applied RCP-SSP framework, which seeks to embrace a range of uncertainties across different plausible future climate and socioeconomic development pathways.

To fully address climate change's global cascading effects, we expand the Computable General Equilibrium model ICES to consider closely bilateral trade among regions and countries, including global supply chain effects. This assessment evaluates: (i) the effects of climate change on land productivity on a global scale. Data on land productivity in different RCPs scenarios are derived from the agro-economic model MAgPIE; (ii) the effects of changes in energy demand for warming and cooling purposes by the productive sectors and households; (iii) the global cascading effects potentially triggered by climate change impacts on three major trade choke points: the Panama Canal, the Turkish Strait, and the Suez Canal.

Please note that the name of the deliverable has changed to better reflect its content which goes beyond what can be possibly presented in one scientific article. Several scientific articles related to this deliverable are in preparation.

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Macro- Economic Impact Assessment of Cascading Effects of Climate Change

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1. Introduction

To understand climate impacts, it is crucial to identify vulnerabilities and causal pathways that interact and lead to second- or third-order effects in the short, medium, and long term. Climate change can amplify existing risks and vulnerabilities in a globalized world, affecting countries and trade partners directly and indirectly. Dellink et al. (2017) reviewed and explored the links between climate change and trade concluding that the competitiveness of countries can be affected directly and indirectly by climate change. One of the limitations of that study, stressed by the authors, is the use of a single baseline to analyse climate impacts. Another limitation is the lack of a detailed modelling of bilateral international trade relations, that was based upon the “standard” representation provided by computable general equilibrium modelling (in the specific case that of the GTAP model). In the present work we consider a wider range of socio-economic development and climate change scenarios adopting a framework based on Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs) and Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), as discussed in section 3 and more extensively in Carter *et al.* (2020). Furthermore, we developed a new module in the ICES Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model, that we used in this assessment (for a description see Bodirsky et al. 2020), based on the latest available data from the GTAP Multi-Regional Input-Output (MRIO) database (Carrico *et al.*, 2020) to better represent and track bilateral trade flows.

The literature offers some examples where detailed dataset on bilateral international trade are integrated with CGE models. Some studies focus on the role of trade policies in boosting Global Value Chains (GVCs) and their potential effects on vertical specialization and countries’ positioning in the GVCs (Salvatici, 2020; Greenville *et al.*, 2019a; Greenville et al., 2017). Greenville *et al.* (2019b) explore the dynamic effects of GVC participation on agri-food sector development and transformation. In their study, they analyze the dynamic GVC effects between 2004 and 2014 of the global economic crisis in 2008/2009 and of the food price spikes in 2007/2008. Greenville *et al.* (2019c) explore the impact that trade and agri-food GVC participation has on labor returns and employment levels, not only within the agricultural sectors, but across other sectors of the economy. However, none of these studies consider the connection between agri-food GVCs and climate change impacts. Indeed, cascading effects of climate change can emerge from an increasingly complex cross-sectoral and multi-regional value chain particularly in the agri-food sector.

Methodologically, GVCs have been studied with different approaches (Jones, Demirkaya and Bethmann, 2019): micro-level analysis using supply chain management, micro-level firm surveys, macro-level input-output, partial, general equilibrium and gravity models. Qualitative, microdata-based products or industry case studies can provide in-depth information on the configuration and characteristics of a specific supply chain. However, they lack a comprehensive, macro-level picture of the gap between trade in value added and gross trade, as well as the economy’s participation and positioning in global production chains. Macro-economic approaches, and CGE models specifically, can address this issue although with some caveats. As pointed out in the GVC literature (Koopman *et al.*, 2012; Koopman *et al.* 2014; Jones *et al.*, 2019), conventional trade statistics, such as the Balassa’s revealed comparative advantage index, that are common outcomes of macro- models, cause a

“double-counting” problem depending mainly on intermediate goods crossing borders multiple times. One caveat relates to possible overestimation of the domestic value-added content of exports. This could be an issue, for instance, when applying a standard CGE model. To address this shortcoming, the idea is to exploit MRIO tables and indicators to develop a different mathematical treatment of international trade in CGE models, as developed in Walmsley and Minor (2016). We follow their approach to revise the ICES specification of international trade as extensively described in section 2.1.

In this deliverable we conduct a macro-economic assessment of cross-border climate change impacts using the global CGE framework of the ICES model. Section 2 explains the ICES model's structure in its standard set up and then, it details main changes implemented to improve its ability to describe trade relations among countries. Section 3 presents the scenarios for the analysis. Section 4 describes the impacts (or shocks) to the agricultural sector, the energy sector, and maritime transport sector. In Section 5, we present and discuss results. Finally, in Section 6 we conclude.

2. The ICES Model

The Intertemporal Computable Economic System (ICES) Model is a standard neoclassical recursive-dynamic general equilibrium model based on the GTAP-E model (Burniaux and Truong, 2002). The calibration year of the ICES model is 2014 according to GTAP version 10a (Aguiar et al., 2019). This database provides a series of interlinked Social Accounting Matrices (SAMs) that give a comprehensive account of payments among productive sectors, final uses (private and public consumption, and investment), trade, and factor income distribution. For this analysis, we enrich the database with the GTAP Multi Regional Input Output (MRIO) database (Carrico *et al.* 2020) which allows for a more detailed tracing of international trade flows among countries. This is an improvement over the original GTAP database, where imports could be traced only by origins and destinations, but not in terms of their uses.

The GTAP database features 141 countries/macro regions and 65 sectors. In this exercise, regional and sectoral detail (reported in Appendix A) has been chosen following the indications from CASCADES WP4 and WP5. Regional aggregation identifies key regions for the analysis of the two WPs. For instance, the “Tigris and Euphrates region” has been included to provide useful macroeconomic insights to support the regional debate in WP4. WP5, instead, suggested a list of countries included in its financial analysis. Similarly, the sectoral aggregation chosen was largely based on input from WP5, to match the sectoral focus of its financial exposure analysis.

The recursive dynamic of the model is solved in five-year step. It is driven by capital accumulation process led by endogenous current-period investment. The time span of the analysis is 2015-2070. In what follows, we shall report results for 2030, 2050 and 2070 as representative years for the short, medium, and long term, respectively.

Appendix B provides a more extended description of ICES. The next section describes the major modifications implemented to get a richer representation of supply chain effects.

2.1 The International trade system enriched with the MRIO module

The MRIO database tracks origins of imports breaking them down according to their final uses (public and private consumption, investments, intermediate uses), country sources, and destinations.

This implies that imports by each agent (firm, household or government) are not aggregated anymore into an undifferentiated composite as in the standard specification (see Appendix B). Instead, in each region (r), agents (firms, private households and government) determine and can substitute their imported commodity (i) from the different sources (s). The new specification of international trade is depicted in Figure 1. This has an important consequence: in the standard GTAP model, international trade shocks are averaged across agents and supply sources

disregarding the agent-source linkage and the nature of the underlying traded goods. With the new specification, users' different behaviors can be considered. For example, importing a good which is an intermediate factor of production has a significantly different macroeconomic effect than importing a good for final uses. In the first case, competitiveness, domestic production and hence employment, can rise, in the second case, domestic production and employment can decrease.

$QXFS_{j,i,s,r}$ = Intermediate imports of commodity i in sector j from source s to destination r ; $QXPS_{i,j,s,r}$ = Private household imports of commodity i from source s to destination r ; $QXGS_{i,j,s,r}$ = Government imports of commodity i source s to destination r ; $QMF_{i,j,r}$ = Total imported intermediates of commodity i in sector j in destination r ; $QMP_{i,r}$ = Total imported private consumption of commodity i in destination r ; $QMG_{i,r}$ = Total imported government consumption of commodity i in destination r ; $QDF_{i,j,r}$ = Total domestic intermediates of commodity i in sector j in destination r ; $QDP_{i,r}$ = Total domestic private consumption of commodity i in destination r ; $QDG_{i,r}$ = Total domestic government consumption of commodity i in destination r ; $QF_{i,j,r}$ = Total intermediates of commodity i in sector j in destination r ; $QP_{i,r}$ = Total private consumption of commodity i in destination r ; $QG_{i,r}$ = Total government consumption of commodity i in destination r ;

Figure 1. The international trade structure in ICES with the introduction of the MRIO module

3. Scenarios

This exercise compares alternative scenarios based on combinations of Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs) and Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) (for a complete discussion on the SSP-RCP architecture see Van Vuuren et al., 2014, and Carter et al. 2020).

Our starting point is Carter et al., (2020), (CASCADES deliverable 2.1), defining the scenario space for the project (see Figure 2)

CMIP5 projections	CMIP6 GCMs	SSP		Sustainability	Middle of the Road	Regional rivalry	Inequality	Fossil-fuelled development
		RCP	W/m ²					
$\Delta T_{2081-2100}^*$	<i>n</i>			SSP1	SSP2	SSP3	SSP4	SSP5
3.2-5.4°C	28	8.5‡						Tier 2
Not evaluated	24	7.0‡			Tier 2	Tier 2	Tier 2	Tier 2
2.0-3.7°C	7	6.0‡	Tier 2		Tier 1	Tier 1	Tier 2	Tier 1
1.7-3.3°C	26	4.5	Tier 3		Tier 3	Tier 3	Tier 3	Tier 3
Not evaluated	7	3.4	Tier 3		Tier 3	Tier 3	Tier 3	Tier 3
0.9-2.3°C	26	2.6‡	Tier 2		Tier 2	Tier 2	Tier 2	Tier 1
Not evaluated	10	1.9	Tier 3		Tier 3			

* Global mean temperature change wrt 1850-1900 (includes 0.6°C observed warming to 1986-2005 –IPCC, 2013)

SSP = Shared Socioeconomic Pathway

RCP = Representative Concentration Pathway

■ = Unachievable forcing by 2100

■ = CMIP5 RCPs

‡ = RCP-based climate projections for which ISIMIP impact simulations are available or planned

Figure 2. SSP-RCP combination and prioritization for the CASCADES project

According to Carter et al., (2020), CASCADES scenarios should “map” uncertainty firstly across three Shared Social Economic Pathways (SSPs) representing key differences in “international connectivity levels”. These need then to be contrasted with medium to low climate change scenarios (RCPs). The scenarios chosen, that well represent these characteristics, are the “Tier 1” scenarios namely **SSP2-RCP6.0**, **SSP3-RCP6.0**, **SSP5-RCP6.0** and **SSP5-RCP2.6**.

This analysis thus considers all tier one scenarios, **plus SSP3-RCP2.6** from tier two. The choice has been made to enable a comparison across different social economic developments, given a specific climate scenario (i.e. SSP2-RCP6.0 vs SSP3-RCP6.0 vs SSP5-RCP6.0), and across different climate developments, given a specific social economic scenario (i.e. either SSP3-RCP2.6 vs SSP3-RCP2.6 or SSP5-RCP2.6 vs SSP5-RCP6.0).

As a first step, social economic baselines have been built by calibrating the economic model on the selected SSPs under current climate.

In characterizing SSPs, we considered six dimensions: population/labour force, income growth, land productivity, energy efficiency, fossil fuels prices, and international trade openness. Table 1 summarizes and compares the narratives along these dimensions for each SSP.

Table 1. SSPs narratives along selected dimensions

	SSP2	SSP3	SSP5	Corresponding parameter and adjustment
Total and labor population	Med	High	Low	Total population and total labor force. Target growth rates are based on Kc and Lutz (2017)
Income growth	Med	Low	High	The total factor productivity is adjusted to achieve the targeted GDP. Target growth rate of GDP are based on Dellink <i>et al.</i> (2017b).
Yield growth assumption	Med	Low	High	Primary factor productivity for land. From Wang <i>et al.</i> (2020) we consider their estimates for regional specific land intensity.
Energy efficiency improvement	Med	Low	Med	Intermediate input productivity parameters for energy commodities in all production sectors are diversified between developed and developing countries. For medium we assume an annual increase by 0.56% and 0.63% for developed and developing countries, respectively (based on IEA 2011, 2012, and Bosello & Parrado 2014). For low these annual increases are lowered by 20%.
Fossil fuels prices	Med	Med	High	For medium we consider trends in fossil fuels prices in the period 2014-2050 from EIA database (2020) and then we extend it up to 2070. For high we assume this trend decreases by 20%
International trade openness	Med	Low	High	<p>Import tariff rate for all goods For low the import tariff rates for all goods are increased, assuming an additional 33% of base-year tax rate to mimic the emerging trade restriction (following assumptions by Fujimori <i>et al.</i>, 2017). For medium and high we assume no change to base-year tax rate. For low only if the import tax rate in the benchmark year level is at least 80% we do not assume any incremental change from 2020 onwards.</p> <p>Export tax for agricultural and energy goods For low, the export tax rates for energy goods (oil, coal, gas, oil products, and electricity) and agricultural goods are changed to represent the preference of internal consumption instead of exporting. Low assumes an additional 33% of base-year tax rates (following assumptions by Fujimori <i>et al.</i>, 2017). For medium and high assume no change to base-year tax rate. For low only if the export tax rate in the benchmark year level is at least 80% we do not assume any incremental change from 2020 onwards.</p>

RCP scenarios are then added to the socioeconomic baselines by introducing RCP-specific climate change impacts, as discussed in section 4 below. These **simulations** represent the **climate change impact scenarios that are compared to their corresponding baselines in the subsequent analysis.**

4. Impacts

4.1 Impacts on agriculture

The first assessment is related to how climate change impacts in the agricultural sector propagated via trade. Climate impacts are derived from the MAgPIE model (Dietrich *et al.* 2019). Here, climate effects on yield are simulated using the MRI-ESM2-0 climate model to perturb the process-based LPJML5 crop model (Von Bloh *et al.*, 2017). Modelled yield changes are a weighted average of irrigated and rainfed yields without any management change, supposing a constant irrigated area. They, therefore, isolate the climate change effect on yields through the time period 2010-2100. The starting year 2010 is considered representative of the current climate situation, while future years represent incremental climate changes with respect to the current situation.

ICES has less agricultural sectors than MAgPIE, therefore a mapping between the two model is needed (as reported in Table 2). Input data from MAgPIE are aggregated according to the ICES regional aggregation (as in appendix A).

ICES - Description	MAgPIE				
Rice: seed, paddy (not husked)	<i>Rice</i>				
Wheat: seed, other	<i>Temperate cereals</i>				
Other Grains: maize (corn), sorghum, barley, rye, oats, millets, other cereals	<i>Maize</i>	<i>Tropical cereals</i>			
Vegetables & Fruits: vegetables, fruit and nuts, edible roots and tubers, pulses	<i>Fruits Vegetables Nuts</i>	<i>Groundnuts</i>	<i>Pulses</i>	<i>Tropical roots</i>	<i>Potatoes</i>
Oil Seeds: oil seeds and oleaginous fruit	<i>Sunflower</i>	<i>Soybean</i>	<i>Oilpalms</i>	<i>Other oil crops incl rapeseed</i>	
Cane & Beet: sugar crops	<i>Sugar beet</i>	<i>Sugar cane</i>			
Fibres crops	<i>Cotton seed</i>				
Other Crops: stimulant; spice and aromatic crops; forage products; plants and parts of plants used primarily in perfumery, pharmacy, or for insecticidal, fungicidal or similar purposes; beet seeds (excluding sugar beet seeds) and seeds of forage plants; natural rubber in primary forms or in plates, sheets or strip, living plants; cut flowers and flower buds; flower seeds, unmanufactured tobacco; other raw vegetable materials nec	<i>Forage</i>				

Table 2. Mapping of crop types between MAgPIE and ICES model

To compute the shocks to feed the ICES model, we assume 2014 as the base year level of yield production under current climate change, and compute 5-year steps percentage changes of land productivity. These shocks are RCP specific, but the same across SSPs. For instance, the same shock is applied in both SSP3-RCP6.0 and SSP5-RCP6.0. The cumulative shocks per crops, regions and RCPs in 2070 are reported in Appendix C.

As discussed in section 3, the SSP baselines already contain evolution of land productivity by crop. Accordingly, climate change impacts on yields from MAgPIE are incremental shocks on land productivity by crop.

4.2 Impacts on energy demand

Climate change impacts on energy demand are taken from the H2020 project COACCH (Schleypen *et al.* 2019). The starting points are the econometric estimates of energy-to-temperature demand elasticity for electricity, petroleum products, and natural gas for agriculture, industry, services and the residential sector by De Cian and Sue Wing (2017). Then, projections of regional energy demand are found combining these elasticities with high-resolution ensemble-mean temperature projections from three Regional Climate Models (RCMs): KNMI RACMO22E, IPSL-CM5A-MR, and CNRM-CM5, and from one Global Climate Model (GCMs): MPI-ESM-LR. This boils down to implementing in the ICES model 12 different impacts (i.e. the number of energy carriers times the number of economic activities) for each RCP.

Changes in energy demand in the agriculture, industry and services sectors have been modeled as changes in the sectoral energy efficiency. Note that the baseline scenarios are also characterized by SSP-specific evolutions of energy efficiency. Accordingly, climate induced changes in energy demand are introduced as a further shock on the sectoral energy efficiency. To increase (decrease) energy demand we imposed a lower (higher) efficiency in the use of energy in the sector.

A different procedure has been used in the case of the residential sector. Energy demand shifts are obtained imposing exogenous shocks to household energy expenditure while keeping fixed the household budget constraint. This implies a re-adjustment of household consumption across all consumption items.

The cumulative shocks per energy carriers, regions and RCPs in 2070 are reported in Appendix D.

4.3 Impacts on maritime chokepoints

The effects of choke points on trade have been analyzed mainly in relation to energy markets and food production. In the energy sector there is a large literature that recognizes the geopolitical aspects of choke points (Emmerson and Stevens, 2012). In the food production sector, the most recent studies on the impact of global choke points recognize the role of climate change (Bailey and Wellesley, 2017). According to Bailey and Wellesley (2017), climate change is increasing the threat of disruption to global trade. It is expected that it will increase the frequency and severity of extreme weather events, leading to more regular closures of chokepoints and greater wear and tear on infrastructure. Rising sea levels will also threaten the integrity of port operations and coastal storage infrastructure and will increase their vulnerability to storm surges. Climate change is also expected to aggravate drivers of conflict and instability. It will also lead to more frequent harvest failures, increasing the risk of governments imposing ad hoc export controls.

In this work we concentrate on analysing the effects of interruptions in three choke points, selected by the team of Chatham House, consistent with a climate change narrative. We evaluate the impact of the interruptions in the Panama Canal, Suez-Canal, and the Turkish Strait. The simulations consist of static shocks - i.e. the analysis is conducted on one representative year - to bilateral trade among countries that uses/served by the Choke Points (CP). The reference year is 2030 in the SSP2 scenario. The nature of the risks associated with the chokepoints is diverse, but they are all connected to climate change (see section 5.3). In the case of the Panama Canal, the simulation replicates the possible consequences of episodes of prolonged droughts, that have been historically observed, the most recent in 2016, that could impede the correct functioning of mobile barriers. In the case of the Suez Canal the simulation analyses a blockade consequent high wind speeds and dust storm. A similar event (aggravated by a rare heat wave in the region) occurred in March 2021, blowing the vessel off course and reducing visibility for navigation. Strong winds have previously delayed shipping traffic or closed the Suez Canal on at least two occasions in December 2010 and February 2015. The final simulation replicates a possible closure driven by a conflict in the Middle East, that we assumed to be exacerbated by climate change.

The data on connecting origin - destinations through CPs is provided by Chatham House. The shocks (interruption in bilateral trade) on CPs are implemented in ICES as a technological change coefficient which affects negatively specific bilateral trade.

5. Results

5.1. Macroeconomic and cascading effects of climate change impacts on agriculture

To isolate the effect of international spillovers derived from agricultural commodities international trade, for each SSP-RCP combination we run three alternative “regional implementations” with a different regional specification of the shocks. The complete picture is provided by the “**World**” scenario where climate change impacts affect all countries. To isolate the spillover effects to and from the EU the “**Europe**” scenario assumes climate change impacts would occur just in the EU and the “**RoW**” scenario that they would occur just outside the EU.

Macroeconomic impacts

Directing the interested reader to the appendix C for further detail, we firstly summarize the major trends in land productivity that build the input for the simulation. Crop yields changes are heterogeneous across crop and regions; however, rice and other grains show, on average, positive reaction to climate change peaking to roughly 18% in Turkey in RCP2.6 and to 35% in Australia in RCP6.0 in 2070. All the positive effects are due to the effect of CO₂ fertilization captured by the LPJmL/MAGPIE model. Losses are more widespread for “other cereals” and wheat where the largest loser is Thailand with a potential yield decline of nearly 60% in RCP2.6 and 80% in RCP6.0. There are also regions, like the “Tigris and Euphrates” area or Paraguay where the yields of almost all cereal crops decline. Amongst non-cereal crops, cane beet and fiber crops yields seem the more negatively affected by climate change, while the picture for vegetable and fruits is mixed. In the Asian region declines can reach almost 10% in Thailand, 3% in Indonesia and “rest of Asia” in RCP6.0 in 2070. In other regions yield gains are projected with a maximum of 30% in Australia in RCP6.0 in 2070.

Figure 3 then presents the GDP changes due to climate change impacts on agriculture for 2030, 2050 and 2070, considering the “**World**” scenario where all regions are hit by climate change. Overall, GDP impacts are moderate, lower than 0.6% of the baseline GDP, they tend to be higher in RCP6 than in RCP 2.6 and increase over time. The most affected regions are the rest of Asia, Transition Economies, Thailand and the Tigris Euphrates region. Looking at the differences across socio-economic scenarios, SSP2 shows higher variability in country results, followed by SSP3 and then SSP5.

Figure 3. GDP variations due to climate change impacts on agriculture

These intra-scenario differences are explained by the market adaptation features embedded in each SSP storyline. One extreme is represented by SSP3 which features lower economic growth and a more fragmented world with relatively lower international trade. In contrast, the SSP5 scenario pictures higher economic growth and lower trade restriction. Indeed, climate change impacts are stronger and more diversified in the SSP3 than in the SSP5 scenario because trade operates as a smoothing mechanism injecting flexibility in the market and an easier adaptation to adverse shocks.

Against this background, all the European regions show negligible GDP impacts with East_EU registering even small benefits.

An indication of the international spillover effects is highlighted in Figure 4. For all the EU areas, except East_EU, impacts outside the EU in fact decrease possible gain or amplify losses (“Europe” vs “World” scenarios), moreover most of the GDP losses within Europe are explained by these “spillovers” driven mainly through international trade channels (“RoW” vs “World” scenarios). In the East_EU gains are amplified by spillovers except in the SSP5.

Figure 4. GDP variations due to climate change impacts on agriculture on EU regions under three different regional implementations of climate impacts.

Sectoral impacts

GDP impacts are generally small. This is partly explained by the relative low share in value added of the agricultural sector that, for instance, in East Asian countries (excluding high income countries) is 8.4% and in the EU area is around 1.6%¹. We then focus on the sectoral level to better highlight the potential cascading effects. Figure 5 details the impacts on the agricultural sectors considered by the ICES model and the food-industry aggregate for 2050. At this level of granularity, impacts are higher.

In the hypothetical case where only Europe was hit by climate change (“**Europe**” in figure) production changes could range between -10% for Fiber Crops in Western Mediterranean EU (Med_EU) to +10% for Wheat in Eastern Mediterranean EU (Rest_Med_EU). The “**RoW**” scenario emphasizes that spillover effects are detrimental to EU sectoral output in most SSP-RCP combinations. These effects are also passed to the Food Industry although the output reduction there is lower than 0.4%.

¹ Data for 2020, World Bank Indicators available at <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NV.AGR.TOTL.ZS>

Figure 5. Variations in sectoral output due to climate change impacts on agriculture for EU regions in 2050

Competitiveness effects

To conduct a more in-depth examination of the competitive performances of EU sectors as they are impacted by cascading effects, we focus on export changes and the revealed competitiveness advantage (RCA) of the EU agricultural and food industries. The RCA is an indicator that compares the share of a sector's exports over the country's total with the sector's average share at the world level. If the RCA is higher than one it means that that country has a revealed comparative advantage for that specific sector. We also focus our analysis on the "RoW" scenario that highlights what the non-EU area would transmit to the EU.

Firstly, Figure 6 presents a scatter plot with the revealed comparative advantage (RCA) indicator on the y axis and the share of exports over production on the x-axis for the baseline projections of agricultural sectors in 2050. A line is drawn when the RCA is equal to 1 to better indicate comparative advantages (symbol above that line). The size of the symbol denotes the value of real output to give a clear idea of the relative importance of the sector within Europe.

For instance, according to the baseline projection in 2050, Wheat and Vegetable & Fruits for Med_EU, Other Grains for East_EU, cane beet in Med and North_EU are sectors that show a comparative advantage in all SSPs. The most important sectors from the production point of view are Wheat, Vegetables & Fruits, and Other Crops. The more export-orientated sectors are Wheat, Vegetables & Fruits (Figure 11 in Appendix C reports data for 2030 and 2070).

Figure 7 reports the same type of information for the Food Industry.

Figure 6. Sectoral production, exports and RCA for agricultural sectors in European regions by 2050

Figure 7. Sectoral production, exports and RCA for the Food industry in European regions in 2050

Figure 8 reports the changes in RCA and share of export over production that climate change outside the EU would induce in the EU in the different RCP and SSP combinations in 2050 compared with the baseline.

Effects on competitiveness are rather small, even though negative, with a partial exception of the wheat market, if compared with export contraction. In other words, climate change impacts on agriculture would “cascade” on the EU with foreign demand reduction of the EU agricultural and food sectors, but without changing too much the competitiveness ranking.

Export reduction can be concerning though. Most affected sectors by cascading effects, thus those somehow more exposed to impacts outside the EU, are Rice in Med_EU in SSP2 and SSP3 (more than 25% export decline wrt baseline), Wheat and Oil seeds (around 5-12% export decline wrt baseline) in Med_EU. The Wheat sectors also register the highest reduction in RCA although the EU keeps its comparative advantage. There are also some sectors that could improve their exports and comparative advantage such as Vegetable & fruits in East_EU, Wheat in East_EU and Rest_Med_EU and Other corps in Most EU regions

It is interesting to note that the SSP5-driven simulations show the lowest deviations from the baseline both in terms of RCA and exports. This confirms a higher “adaptive capacity” shown by markets with higher growth and no trade frictions. Conversely, most cases with higher deviations from the baseline appear in the fragmented SSP3 scenario. SSP2 is in the middle. Negative impacts are larger in RCP6.0 than in RCP2.6 with the exception of Other crops and Vegetable & Fruits.

Figure 8. Climate change impacts of agriculture on Trade and competitiveness for Europe in 2050

The food industry in Europe in 2050 offers a similar picture, even though impacts are smaller when compared to agricultural sectors as effects are more indirect (Figure 9). It demonstrates a negligible loss in the comparative advantage along with a reduction in exports in all regions that could reach 1%. Lower impacts in the SSP5 scenario are also confirmed as well as SSP3 being the scenario with slightly higher impacts than SSP2.

Figure 9. Climate change impacts of agriculture on trade and competitiveness of the EU food industry in 2050

5.2. Macroeconomic and cascading effects of climate change impacts on energy demand

In the case of energy demand, the macroeconomic (and sectoral) impacts analyzed are a consequence of the change in heating and cooling behavior by firms and households. Differently from the impacts on agriculture, that were triggered by a change in the supply side of the market (changes in land productivity or yields), these affect the demand-side, or, said differently, consumers' preferences. This implies that the economic consequences that are assessed are mostly re-distributional. Firstly, across consumption items: if firms and households decide/have to spend more or less money for their energy needs, or for some specific energy vectors (say gas vs electricity) then they will devote less or more of their resources respectively to buy other factors of production, goods and services. Secondly, across agents: more energy demand from households can be an additional stress on their budget, but also a source of additional revenue for energy producers. Therefore, a change, say a reduction, in energy demand can translate either into a gain or a loss for the whole economy. These issues need to be considered for the correct interpretation of the results. Furthermore, given the paramount role of substitution effects in agents

preferences in driving the results, and their volatility, we deem less interesting/informative to conduct a simulation that isolates the “rest of the world effects” as we did in the agriculture case. We rather focus on assessing the overall effects of shifts in energy demand developing a full global analysis.

Directing the interested reader to the appendix D for further detail, we firstly summarize the major trends in energy demand, that builds the input for the simulation. Increasing temperatures typically lead to an increase in energy demand for cooling, more evident in hot countries and to a decreased demand for warming more evident in cold countries. According to our data, this cooling effect is widespread globally, it affects particularly electricity demand of households and of the service sector where most of the activity is indoor. Nonetheless increased electricity demand is projected also for industry and in some regions, most notably China, Canada, South Africa and Australia, also in agriculture. For energy vectors different from electricity (oil and gas) the situation is more nuanced also because they are not only used for heating/cooling purposes. Reduction in households’ fossil fuel demand can be observed in the EU. In the other regions, fossil fuel demand shows little changes and, in the case of natural gas, it can slightly increase. The industry and the agricultural sectors depict a generalized albeit small increase of oil products and gas demand whereas the service sector decreases the demand of fossil gas energy.

The combined effect on GDP highlights three types of macro regions: The EU and Japan can moderately gain from the energy demand re-composition (+1% of GDP in the East and Med EU in 2070), China and especially India (-8% in 2070 in the SSP5-RCP6.0 scenario combination) can lose. In between there are all the other regions showing, in 2070 when the impacts are larger, GDP changes between + or -0.5% (Figure 10). As expected, the stronger climate signal RCP6.0 almost always produces higher impacts than the lower climate signal RCP2.6, while SSP3, with its trade restrictions, on average, depicts larger losses, but lower gains than SSP2 and SSP5. Before 2070 with the exceptions of India, China, and Rest of Med_Eu, all GDP changes are below 0.5%.

Figure 11 illustrates, for 2050, the EU area performance. Overall, the re-compositions effects triggered by shifts in energy demand patterns, that often compensate each other, do not impact too much the macroeconomic results of the region, although the Rest of Mediterranean EU which includes Mediterranean islands like Cyprus and Malta, particularly hot, can indeed experience losses due to increased energy expenditures. Albeit still moderate, the changes are larger than those induced by agricultural impacts (previous section). This highlights the relatively larger importance of the energy sector in the production of value added, compared with agriculture.

To summarize competitiveness effects in the EU, Figure 12 reports changes in terms of trade. These are measured by the export to import price ratio. A worsening, meaning that more exports would be needed to pay for a given amount of import, is an indication of a loss of international competitiveness. Changes are tiny, implying that competitiveness effects, are negligible. It is however interesting to note that, by 2070, except for East_EU, all the EU area worsens, and this independently upon the possible moderate GDP gains highlighted above. This suggests that the competitiveness of a net energy importer like the EU can be particularly exposed to shocks in the energy markets.

Figure 10. Climate change impacts on energy demand: effects on GDP

Figure 11. Climate change impacts on energy demand: effects on EU macro regional GDP in 2050

Figure 12. Climate change impacts on energy demand: terms of trade effects in EU regions in 2050

Economic impacts are more appreciable analyzing the sectoral picture especially focusing on the energy and energy-intensive sectors that should be more affected by energy demand changes and possible price effects (Figure 13). By midcentury, as far as energy sectors are concerned, all the EU areas experience an increase in electricity production peaking to a +7% in the Rest of Mediterranean EU in response to the higher demand for cooling. On the contrary oil production declines everywhere. Here, it is interesting to focus on the Rest_of_EU data (-0.25, -0.5% production contraction) that includes Norway, the 13th largest world oil producer. On the contrary, energy intensive sectors follow macroeconomic trends (i.e. the GDP results): therefore, when there are gains, sectoral production increases, when there are losses, it declines.

Figure 13. Climate change impacts on energy demand: Impacts on EU region energy, and EITE sectoral production in 2050

Sectoral Competitiveness effects

A sectoral picture of competitiveness and cascading effects in the EU is offered by changes in RCA and exports. The starting position of the EU projected for 2050 regarding energy, energy intensive sectors exposed to international competition (these are also known as EITE sectors – i.e. energy intensive trade exposed sectors: chemicals, iron and steel, non-metallic mineral product, non-ferrous minerals) and of macro sectors (agriculture, energy, industry, services) is represented in Figure 14 and Figure 15 respectively.

As expected, being the EU a net energy importer, most of the EU regions are projected to depict an RCA lower than one in energy productions with the notable exception of electricity; the picture is more mixed for other EITE sectors. Also agriculture highlights a Relative Compared “Disadvantage” for the EU while in services’ production the EU, with the exception of East_EU, has an advantage.

Climate change is not altering this picture entailing changes only by a few % points (Figure 16, Figure 17). This is consistent with the already noted negligible changes in macro regional terms of trade, meaning that readjustments in energy demand, eventually wash out reciprocally. It also occurs that RCP6.0 impacts are larger than RCP2.6 impacts.

This said, the Rest of_Med EU, the region that experienced losses either in terms of trade or GDP, appears in the bottom-left panel in almost all tables, denoting a worsening in sectoral RCA and a decrease in export. Notably it has improved performance in electricity and (other) non fossil energy production. Med_EU slightly improves its RCA in services, non-ferrous and non-metallic minerals, chemicals and iron and steel, coupled with an export increase reaching a maximum of 4% in services. Med EU worsens in all other sectors, but exports tend to increase anyway. East_EU North EU and Rest of EU are better off in energy intensive sectors, but worse off in services.

Figure 14. Sectoral production, share of exports over production and RCA for EU-regions energy and EITE sectors in 2050

Figure 15. Sectoral production, share of exports over production and RCA for EU-regions macro-sectors in 2050

Figure 16. Climate change impacts on energy demand: RCA and exports of energy and EITE sectors in EU regions in 2050 (% change wrt baseline)

Figure 17. Climate change impacts of energy demand. RCA and exports of macro sectors in EU regions in 2050 (% change wrt baseline)

5.3. Macroeconomic and cascading effects of maritime chokepoints interruption.

In this section, we address the economic effects of possible interruptions in maritime chokepoints on the European Union and the global economy. Climate change effects on maritime transportation in choke points have been registered at least since 1998. In this exercise we consider three of these chokepoints: the Panama Canal, the Suez Canal and the Strait of Turkey. We then simulate the occurrence of three different adverse events that could be triggered by climate change (see box). In the case of the Panama Canal, the simulation replicates the possible consequences of prolonged droughts which reduces navigation capacity by one-fifth. A similar event has been observed in 2016. In the case of the Suez Canal the simulation assesses the effect of high wind speeds and dust storm that can impede navigation similarly to what witnessed in March 2021. In that month strong wind provoked the grounding of the 400-metre Ever Given container ship in the Suez Canal, causing a blockage to this vital waterway with huge economic losses. Strong winds have previously delayed shipping traffic or closed the Suez Canal on at least two occasions in December 2010 and February 2015. In the case of the Strait of Turkey the simulation tests the possible effects of a conflict in the Middle East region that prevents navigation. We assume that climate change is an exacerbating factor of conflict. All these events cannot be predicted with certainty, however, they can become more frequent in the future because of both increasing climate change stressors and expansion of trade. Finally, our analysis will be restricted on four agricultural commodities: rice, wheat, other grains, and oil seeds.

BOX: The narrative on chokepoint impacts

Panama Canal

A strong El Niño event brings long periods of dry weather to Central America, causing water levels to drop in the Gatún and Miraflores lakes either side of the Panama Canal and leading to the introduction of depth restrictions on vessels transiting the canal. Similar, El Niño induced events occurred in 2016, affecting nearly a fifth of vessels using the canal, and prior to that in 1997-1998. It is plausible to expect that a more severe future event may reduce water levels for longer and to a greater degree, affecting half of all vessels using the Panama Canal. As the largest vessels – with the largest freight capacities – will be disproportionately affected, and as canal throughput of agricultural commodities is seasonal, then the proportion of produce affected could be even greater. Although many vessels would be able to continue to transit the Panama Canal, the restrictions on the amount of cargo they could carry will affect the economics of the passage.

For the purposes of simple illustration, we assume that the depth restrictions apply for six months during which 75 per cent of annual agricultural throughput occurs, and that the 50 per cent of vessels affected are responsible for carrying 70 per cent of all agricultural commodities.

Therefore, the event lasting half a year and affecting half of vessels disrupts 53 per cent of annual agricultural produce transiting the canal (0.75×0.7).

Turkish Straits

The risks of future and protracted conflicts in the Middle East remain and may be exacerbated by climate impacts in the region, which will have continued implications for the security of the region's chokepoints. The wars in Syria and Yemen persist, for example, with little hope for imminent peace and the risk of armed conflict in Turkey is non-trivial: the country shares borders with conflict-ravaged Syria and Iraq; there have been a number of terrorist incidents in the region in the last decade; and the July 2016 coup attempt and subsequent government crackdown have highlighted concerns about stability. The coup led to halting of traffic through the Bosphorus Strait; although this lasted only a few hours it threw into sharp relief the ease with which this key artery for food trade may be shut down when insecurity peaks. In 2015 and 2016 tensions between Turkey and Russia rose, with their clash over the war in Syria fuelled further by military manoeuvres in the Turkish Straits and Turkey's shooting down of a Russian military jet in November 2015. In this period, Turkish naval fleets obstructed Russian vessels transiting the Bosphorus Strait and there was a reported spike in the number of Russian warships using the strait. Although there was a rapprochement between Turkey and Russia in 2017 and few expect the Turkish Straits to be permanently blocked in the near-term, future blockading of this strategic chokepoint is not beyond the realms of possibility should bilateral tensions escalate again.²

For the purposes of simple illustration, we consider the possibility that climate impacts in Syria lead to re-escalation of Syrian conflict, including between proxy powers of Turkey and Russia. Consequently, Turkey blockades vessels transiting the Turkish Straits for the 2 months of the year during which 40 per cent of Black Sea breadbasket harvests are typically transported. We assume that some of this harvest can be held in storage facilities in the region and shipped after the blockade is lifted, but that 30 per cent of the crop is spoiled. Therefore, we assume 12 per cent of annual agricultural commodity trade through the straits are affected (0.4×0.3).

Suez Canal and Strait of Bab al-Mandab

As witnessed in March 2021 following the grounding of the 400-metre Ever Given container ship in the Suez Canal, blockages to this vital waterway can be extremely disruptive to global trade. More than 400 vessels were stranded in the Mediterranean and the Red Sea and it is estimated that nearly \$60 billion of trade was held up in just six days. In this event, high wind speeds and a dust storm – aggravated by a rare heat wave in the region that dried the soil and made it more prone to become windswept – were attributed to blowing the vessel off course and reducing visibility for navigation. Although rare, strong winds have previously delayed shipping traffic or closed the Suez Canal on at least two occasions in December 2010 and February 2015. It is possible that climate change could have contributed to the extreme large-

² <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2017/06/chokepoints-and-vulnerabilities-global-food-trade>

scale weather pattern responsible for the 2021 sandstorm: there was a very amplified and wavy jet stream pattern in the region at the time, with a strong ridge of high pressure over the Middle East and a strong trough of low pressure just to its west over the central Mediterranean Sea – both features were about two standard deviations from the mean. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in similar “global weirding” extreme jet stream patterns in summer, because of a phenomenon known as quasi-resonant amplification (QRA), potentially due to rapid Arctic heating.³

For the purposes of simple illustration, we consider the possibility that a similar QRA-driven event could also drive strong storm surges in the Red Sea’s Gulf of Suez at the southern end of the canal,⁴ and thus not just affect vessels in the canal but also lead to infrastructure damage at Port Taofik where the Red Sea and Suez Canal meet. We assume such damages could render the canal unnavigable for 6 weeks whilst damage is repaired, and ships are refloated. Under this scenario, 12 per cent of agricultural-commodity throughput would be affected (6/52).

We assume that these events will take place in 2030. Thus, differently from previous exercises, what we simulate is the one-year economic implication of the choke point disruption. Table 3 shows the volume of trade expected to transit through such chokepoints (based on bilateral trade patterns projected by the ICES model in 2030 considering the baseline for the SSP2 scenario and the proportion of the global bilateral trade through choke points). The choke points under consideration represent altogether 38% of the global trade in those commodities. Table 3 illustrates the inputs to the economic assessment.

Table 4 exemplifies how the shocks on imports of the different commodities in bilateral connections is implemented.

Table 3: Pre-Shock Value of trade through maritime chokepoints in 2030 (MM\$ \$2014)

	Panama Canal	Turkish Strait	Suez Canal	Total Trade
Rice	194.2	168.7	214.4	2623.0
Wheat	6322.0	8225.2	7240.8	54931.0
Other Cereals	8517.0	7092.6	4983.0	51644.0
Oil Seeds	24499.1	4789.7	4200.0	93015.0
Sub total	39532.3	20276.2	16638.2	202213.0

Source: Based on ICES baseline SSP2 and Chatham House information on specific shares of bilateral trade through choke points in 2018.

³ <https://yaleclimateconnections.org/2021/03/suez-canal-shutdown-shows-vulnerability-of-global-economy-to-extreme-events>

⁴ Cf. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/jmse3020356>

Table 4: Trade Affected in Choke Points (%)

	Panama Canal	Turkish Strait	Suez Canal
Nature of the event	Extreme dry seasons (2016 the most recent) reduce for 6 month the transit of big carriers	8 weeks closure due to conflict (during which 40% of Black Sea harvests are exported, 30% is spoiled)	6 weeks closure (strong winds)
Proportion of annual trade estimated to be affected by the CP event	54%	12%	12%
Value of trade at risk (MM\$ 2014)	20952	2433	1997

Source: Based on ICES baseline SSP2 and Chatham House information on specific shares of bilateral trade through choke points in 2018.

Table 5: Computing shocks in bilateral trade from chokepoint operation interruption – An Example

	Panama	Turkish Strait	Suez Canal
Commodity	Rice	Other Grains	Wheat
a) Main Trade Partner affected in volume (origin-destination)	USA – China	Ukraine – MENA	North Europe – MENA
b) Base-line trade	6581	2326.4	1711.4
c) % trade affected in CP	54%	12%	12%
d) % bilateral trade through choke point	75.11%	100%	77.30%
e) Trade reduction: $I = (-1) * (b) * (d)$	-2669.2	-279.1	-158.7
f) Specific bilateral Shock in imports (to implement in ICES): $(f) = (e) / (b) * 100$	-40.6%	-12%	-9%

Source: Based on ICES baseline SSP2 and Chatham House information on specific shares of bilateral trade through choke points in 2018.

In reporting the results, we focus on changes in GDP, production in the food industry, and consumer prices. Percent changes in GDP are “small” as expected, nonetheless, in absolute terms, economic losses can be far from negligible. Chokepoint interruption seems to be more damaging for Eastern countries and, in the case of Panama, for Canada and Argentina. Among the EU regions only Northern Europe depicts a negative impact, equivalent to \$ 10.2Million. Other countries exhibiting significant losses are Canada \$ 215.6 Mill. and Russia \$ 98.8 Mill. The effects transmitted to the EU by Panama Canal are larger than that of the other chokepoints. This is a direct consequence of the larger trade volumes in the commodity considered and of the larger shock affecting the chokepoint.

Table 6. CP and Variation of GDP in Percentage Points and losses in Mill. \$ (2014)

	Panama Canal	Turkish Strait	Suez Canal	Total Losses in Mill. \$ 2014
1 North_EU	0.0053	-0.0001	0.0019	-10.2
2 Med_EU	0.0086	0.0007	0.0031	
3 Rest_Med_EU	0.0044	0.0007	0.0029	
4 East_EU	0.0026	0.0009	0.0022	
5 RestEurope	0.0028	0.0000	0.0010	
6 Canada	-0.009	0.000	0.000	-215.6
7 USA	0.005	0.000	0.001	
8 Mexico	0.008	0.000	0.001	
9 Argentina	-0.001	0.000	0.000	-11.5
10 Brazil	0.010	0.000	0.000	
11 Paraguay	0.033	0.000	0.000	
12 RestofLACA	0.084	0.000	0.001	-0.3
13 TE	0.001	0.000	-0.001	-0.9
14 Russia	0.000	0.001	-0.003	-98.8
15 Ukraine	0.012	-0.005	-0.024	-64.6
16 Kazakistan	-0.001	-0.002	-0.003	-28.9

* The table reports countries-regions with the more significant negative losses. Full results are available upon request.

Effects on EU agricultural commodities production is mixed also because the regions considered are large and intra EU trade can take place which prevents clear-cut conclusions. It is thus more informative to concentrate on the food industry that summarizes the downstream effects of import contractions (Table 7). Food Industry as reported in ICES is a “light” industry that uses agricultural products (rice, wheat, other grains, oil seeds), as inputs. It is interesting to note that in fact all over the EU area, the industry is affected negatively in association with a blockage of the Panama Canal. This confirms that imports of cereal commodities have not only important cascading effects on food production, but also that Panama is a particularly crucial node for that activity in the EU. A similar finding can be derived for the Turkish Strait, but with relevance for the Mediterranean EU regions. The EU food industry is on the contrary less vulnerable to cereal trade risk transmitted by Suez Canal interruption that, instead, seems more concerning for Near East and Asian economies.

Table 7. Food industry production in association with CP interruption (% ch wrt baseline)

	Panama Canal	Turkish Strait	Suez Canal
1 North_EU	-0.047	0.020	0.009
2 Med_EU	-0.056	-0.027	0.034
3 Rest_Med_EU	-0.017	-0.021	0.026
4 East_EU	-0.042	0.036	0.032
5 RestEurope	-0.029	0.005	-0.001
6 Canada	0.527	0.001	0.127
7 USA	0.231	-0.001	0.024
8 Mexico	0.095	0.002	0.022
9 Argentina	1.371	-0.054	0.218
10 Brazil	0.026	0.005	-0.010
11 Paraguay	0.043	0.336	-0.028
12 RestofLACA	-0.126	-0.004	0.009
13 TE	-0.014	-0.180	-0.050
14 Russia	-0.026	-0.137	-0.071
15 Ukraine	-0.353	4.564	1.124
16 Kazakistan	-0.016	-0.682	-0.061
17 Turkey	-0.022	-0.206	-0.033
18 MENA	-0.092	-0.073	-0.202
19 TigEuphrate	0.000	0.010	0.003
20 SSA	-0.026	0.002	0.002
21 SouthAfrica	-0.031	-0.003	-0.014
22 India	-0.039	-0.008	0.042
23 China	-0.027	-0.006	-0.005
24 HongKong	-0.020	-0.007	-0.002
25 Japan	-0.401	-0.002	0.007
26 SouthKorea	-1.042	-0.084	-0.136
27 Taiwan	0.288	0.011	0.042
28 Indonesia	-0.080	-0.016	-0.065
29 Thailand	-0.053	-0.005	-0.034
30 RestAsia	-0.010	-0.006	-0.035
31 Australia	-0.078	0.000	-0.029
32 RoW	0.001	0.013	0.008

Finally, Table 8 reports price effects. We specify the investigation on all the agricultural commodities analyzed by the model, even though, we recall, we have explicit information on direct impacts just for rice, wheat, other grains, and oil seeds. Price trends can offer some insight of the possible impacts on household welfare. Panama Canal interruption highlights a generalized increase in the price of agricultural commodities and food industry. Even though moderate, this is a signal of stress on especially poor households that typically spend a higher share of their

income on basic needs such as food. Contraction in traded volumes through other CP as Suez Canal and Turkish Strait has a more sectoral-specific effect limited to potentially harmful price increases in Other Grains, but lower in magnitude than the Panama Canal. Domestic rice production increases in different regions in Europe under alternative choke points stressors, while total imports decrease, except when shocks occur in the Panama Canal. The full effects of the composition of the supply of commodities on the domestic prices need to be study further.

Table 8: Prices of agricultural commodities in association with CP interruption (% ch wrt baseline)

	1 North_EU	2 Med_EU	3 Rest_Med_EU	4 East_EU	5 RestEurope
1 Rice	0.0232	0.0435	0.0298	0.0988	0.0277
2 Wheat	0.2331	0.2968	0.1865	0.1864	0.0607
3 OtherGrains	0.5724	0.6286	0.2090	0.3418	0.2845
4 VegFruits	-0.0712	-0.0626	-0.0130	0.0041	-0.0452
5 OilSeeds	0.0556	0.0571	0.0831	0.1187	0.1676
6 CaneBeet	0.0229	0.0272	0.0369	0.0386	0.0259
7 FibreCrops	-0.0187	-0.0167	0.0105	0.0221	-0.0005
8 OtherCrops	0.0075	0.0081	0.0057	0.0218	0.0229
15 Food Ind.	0.0205	0.0304	0.0177	0.0234	0.0205

Turkish Strait

	1 North_EU	2 Med_EU	3 Rest_Med_EU	4 East_EU	5 RestEurope
1 Rice	-0.0045	-0.0230	-0.0215	-0.0028	-0.0323
2 Wheat	-0.1811	-0.0475	-0.1360	-0.1836	-0.1033
3 OtherGrains	-0.0766	0.3416	0.2471	-0.1978	-0.1519
4 VegFruits	-0.0115	-0.0140	-0.0348	-0.1348	-0.0229
5 OilSeeds	-0.0295	-0.0373	-0.0336	0.1507	-0.0596
6 CaneBeet	-0.0077	-0.0026	-0.0489	-0.0761	-0.0299
7 FibreCrops	0.0074	-0.0037	0.0010	0.2357	-0.0123
8 OtherCrops	-0.0097	-0.0074	-0.0349	-0.0546	-0.0371
15 Food Ind.	-0.0119	0.0011	-0.0101	-0.0268	-0.0076

Suez Canal

	1 North_EU	2 Med_EU	3 Rest_Med_EU	4 East_EU	5 RestEurope
1 Rice	-0.0143	-0.0747	-0.0076	-0.0613	0.0155
2 Wheat	-0.2841	-0.4607	-0.6220	-0.3924	-0.0900
3 OtherGrains	0.3887	0.1055	-0.1522	-0.2736	0.0326
4 VegFruits	-0.0569	-0.0774	-0.0811	-0.1041	-0.0474
5 OilSeeds	0.0109	-0.0605	0.0414	0.1217	0.1107
6 CaneBeet	-0.0231	-0.0453	-0.1024	-0.0609	-0.0265
7 FibreCrops	-0.0212	-0.0359	-0.0257	-0.0036	-0.0233
8 OtherCrops	-0.0278	-0.0501	-0.0656	-0.0653	-0.0351
15 Food ind.	-0.0109	-0.0202	-0.0186	-0.0224	-0.0066

Table 9. Food industry production in association with CP interruption (% ch wrt baseline)

	Panama Canal	Turkish Strait	Suez Canal
1 North_EU	-0.047	0.020	0.009
2 Med_EU	-0.056	-0.027	0.034
3 Rest_Med_EU	-0.017	-0.021	0.026
4 East_EU	-0.042	0.036	0.032
5 RestEurope	-0.029	0.005	-0.001
6 Canada	0.527	0.001	0.127
7 USA	0.231	-0.001	0.024
8 Mexico	0.095	0.002	0.022
9 Argentina	1.371	-0.054	0.218
10 Brazil	0.026	0.005	-0.010
11 Paraguay	0.043	0.336	-0.028
12 RestofLACA	-0.126	-0.004	0.009
13 TE	-0.014	-0.180	-0.050
14 Russia	-0.026	-0.137	-0.071
15 Ukraine	-0.353	4.564	1.124
16 Kazakistan	-0.016	-0.682	-0.061
17 Turkey	-0.022	-0.206	-0.033
18 MENA	-0.092	-0.073	-0.202
19 TigEuphrate	0.000	0.010	0.003
20 SSA	-0.026	0.002	0.002
21 SouthAfrica	-0.031	-0.003	-0.014
22 India	-0.039	-0.008	0.042
23 China	-0.027	-0.006	-0.005
24 HongKong	-0.020	-0.007	-0.002
25 Japan	-0.401	-0.002	0.007
26 SouthKorea	-1.042	-0.084	-0.136
27 Taiwan	0.288	0.011	0.042
28 Indonesia	-0.080	-0.016	-0.065
29 Thailand	-0.053	-0.005	-0.034
30 RestAsia	-0.010	-0.006	-0.035
31 Australia	-0.078	0.000	-0.029
32 RoW	0.001	0.013	0.008

6. Conclusions

This analysis examined cascading effects transmitted to the EU through climate change impacts on agriculture, on energy demand and stemming from potential interruption of operations through three representative, strategic trade nodes: the Panama Canal, the Turkish Strait and the Suez Canal.

The supply side effects on agricultural commodities seems particularly small on country and macro-regional GDP. These small effects, coupled with the relatively low share of total value added of agriculture in the EU economies, explain also small effects on EU competitive position. Nonetheless, cascading effects are huge. Indeed, we show that yield changes originating outside the EU can explain the majority of changes in the GDP and agricultural sector production performances of the EU (with the partial exception of GDP in the Eastern EU). Moreover, the small effects on GDP, magnify when the analysis is conducted at the sectoral level. For instance, wheat production can reduce by 4.5% in the Mediterranean EU and by 6% in the East EU by midcentury.

In the EU, the energy sector contributes with a higher share to GDP production than agriculture. Hence, cascading effects are expected to be larger. Detecting clear trends however remains difficult because of the redistributive nature of the climate change shocks examined. Indeed energy demand re-composition following temperature changes induces a reallocation of households' and firms' expenditure across different energy vectors, commodities and agents that often compensate each other in the final aggregated economic performance. GDP and terms of trade effects remain moderate, but larger than in the agriculture case. By midcentury, all the EU areas experience an increase in electricity production peaking to a +7% in the Rest of Mediterranean EU in response to the higher demand for cooling. On the contrary oil production declines everywhere. The rest of energy intensive sectors follow the GDP results: therefore, when there are gains, also sectoral production increases, when there are losses, it declines. It is however interesting to note that, by 2070, except for East_EU, all the EU area slightly worsens its competitive position, independently of possible moderate GDP gains. This suggests that the competitiveness of a net energy importer like the EU can be particularly exposed to shocks in energy markets.

The Chokepoint analysis emphasizes the important role of these nodes in impact transmission. Although macroeconomic effects are smaller (but not much smaller if compared to agricultural impacts) than the previous cases, it has to be considered that the shocks examined are not "permanent" like in the case of energy and agriculture, and that only a subset of the agricultural commodities transiting through the nodes is examined. Eventually, the effects on trade have similar impacts of effects on production. This said, GDP impacts from chokepoint interruption are small - this also depending on the huge geo-political blocks we are examining - more negative for Eastern countries and, in the case of Panama blockade, for Canada and Argentina than for the EU. It is however interesting to note that in fact all over the EU area, the food industry production is affected negatively. This confirms that imports of cereal commodities have not only important cascading effects on food production, but also that the Panama Canal is a particularly crucial node for that activity in the EU. A similar

finding can be derived for the Turkish Strait, but with relevance for the Mediterranean EU regions. The EU food industry is on the contrary less vulnerable to cereal trade risk transmitted by Suez Canal interruption that, instead, seems more concerning for Near East and Asian economies.

Appendices

Appendix A. Sectoral and regional aggregation for the ICES model

Table A1: Regional aggregation in the ICES model

ICES regions	Original GTAP countries
North_EU	Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Sweden
Med_EU	France, Greece, Italy, Portugal Spain
Rest_Med_EU	Cyprus, Malta, Slovenia, Croatia
East_EU	Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia
Rest of Europe	United Kingdom, Switzerland, Norway, Rest of Free Trade Association, Albania, Rest of Europe
Canada	Canada
USA	USA
Mexico	Mexico
Argentina	Argentina
Brazil	Brazil
Paraguay	Paraguay
Rest of LACA	Rest of North America, Bolivia, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, Uruguay, Venezuela, Rest of South America, Costa Rica, Guatemala, Honduras, Nicaragua, Panama, EL Salvador, Rest of Central America, Dominican Republic, Jamaica, Puerto Rico, Trinidad and Tobago, Rest of Caribbean
Transition Economies	Belarus, Rest of Eastern Europe, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Rest of Former Soviet Union, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia
Russian Federation	Russian Federation
Ukraine	Ukraine
Kazakhstan	Kazakhstan
Turkey	Turkey
MENA	Bahrain, Islamic Republic of Iran, Israel, Jordan, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia, Rest of North Africa
Tigris Euphrates	Rest of Western Asia
SSA	Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Guinea, Nigeria, Senegal, Togo, Rest of Western Africa, Rest of Central Africa, South Central Africa, Ethiopia, Kenya, Madagascar, Malawi, Mauritius, Mozambique, Rwanda, United Republic of Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Rest of Eastern Africa, Botswana, Namibia, Rest of South African Customs Union
South Africa	South Africa
India	India
China	China
Hong Kong	Hong Kong
Japan	Japan
South Korea	South Korea
Taiwan	Taiwan
Indonesia	Indonesia
Thailand	Thailand
Rest of Asia	Mongolia, Rest of East Asia, Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Lao PDR, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Viet Nam, Rest of Southeast Asia, Bangladesh, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Rest of South Asia
Australia	Australia
ROW	New Zealand, Rest of Oceania, Rest of the World

Table A2: Sectoral aggregation in the ICES model

ICES sectors	Original GTAP sectors
Rice	Rice
Wheat	Wheat
Other grains	Maize (corn), Sorghum, barley, Rye, Oats, Millets, Other cereals
Vegetables and fruits	Vegetables, Fruit and nuts, Edible roots and tubers, Pulses
Oil seeds	Oil seeds, Oleaginous fruit
Cane & beet	Sugar crops
Fibres crops	Fibres crops
Other crops	Other crops
Other Agr-Frs-Fsh	Cattle, Other animal products, Raw milk, Wool, Forestry, Fishing
Coal	Coal
Oil	Oil
Gas	Gas, Gas (manufacture, distribution)
Food industries	Cattle meat, Other meat, Vegetable oils, Dairy products, Processed rice, Sugar and molasses, Other food, Beverages and tobacco products
Light industries	Textiles, Wearing apparel, Leather and related products, Computer, Electronic and optical products, Electrical equipment, Machinery and equipment nec
Other industries	Other Mining Extraction, Lumber, Paper & paper products, Pharmaceuticals, medicinal chemical and botanical products, Rubber & plastics products, Fabricated metal products (except machinery and equipment), Motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers, Other transport equipment, Other Manufacturing (including furniture)
Oil products	Petroleum & Coke
Chemicals non-mineral products	Chemicals, Other non-metallic mineral products
Iron & steel	Iron & Steel
Non-ferrous metals	Non-Ferrous Metals
Electricity- Fossil	Electricity; Steam and air conditioning supply
Electricity- Nuclear	
Electricity- Hydro	
Electricity- Renewables	
Services	Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation activities, Wholesale and retail trade repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles, Accommodation, Food and service activities, Warehousing and support activities, Information and communication, Other Financial Intermediation, Insurance, Real estate activities, Other Business Services nec, Recreation & Other Services, Other Services (Government), Education, Human health and social work, Dwellings
Construction	Building houses, factories, offices, and roads
Other transports	Land transport and transport via pipelines,
Water transports	Water transports
Air transports	Air transports

Appendix B. Description of the ICES model⁵

Productive activities

For each productive sector, a typical firm maximizes its profits given a set of inputs (primary factors and intermediate inputs), the final output and the corresponding prices. This means that factor remuneration equals their marginal costs based on endogenous relative prices. Consistent with Neoclassical theory, the production technology assumes constant returns to scale. Firstly, a capital/energy bundle is formed via a series of nested constant elasticity of substitution (CES) functions which assumes substitutability among different energy sources (gas, oil, coal, petroleum products, and electricity from either fossil or renewable sources). The choice among primary factors (labour, land, and natural resources) and the capital/energy bundle is achieved through a subsequent CES function. This specification allows to move from one combination of primary factors to another as a response in relative prices getting a final value- added/energy composite (VAE). Then, the composite is combined with intermediate inputs in a fixed proportion using a Leontief specification. This means that there is a fixed coefficient linking value added and intermediates because of a technological property of the production function and it is independent of the relative prices. The final price of the output is defined by the price of the value- added composite, the intermediates (gross of taxes imposed on them by the government) and the final output taxes or subsidies.

International trade

ICES follows the standard GTAP model trade structure (known as Armington approach) which allows for substitution between domestic and imported commodities in the domestic market through a two level CES function. Firstly, imports of a similar good (i) sourced from different regions (s) and destined to a region (r) ($QXS_{i,s,r}$) are collected at the borders and translated into a bundle of imports called $QIM_{i,r}$. Then, end users decide the ratio of domestic goods ($QDF_{j,i,r}$, $QDP_{i,r}$, $QDG_{i,r}$, for firms in sector j , households and government, respectively) and import bundle ($QMF_{j,i,r}$, $QMP_{i,r}$, $QMG_{i,r}$) defined by a cost-minimizing decision of domestic purchasers on the base of relative prices of imports and domestic goods (gross of relevant taxes or subsidies). Figure 91 depicts the structure of the international trade.

⁵ For a complete and graphical description of the ICES model visit the site: <https://www.icesmodel.org/>

$QXS_{i,s,r}$ = Imports of commodity i from source s to destination r ; $QIM_{i,r}$ = Composite import of commodity i in destination r ; $QMF_{j,i,r}$ = Total imported intermediates of commodity i in sector j in destination r ; $QMP_{i,r}$ = Total imported private consumption of commodity i in destination r ; $QMG_{i,r}$ = Total imported government consumption of commodity i in destination r ; $QDF_{j,i,r}$ = Total domestic intermediates of commodity i in sector j in destination r ; $QDP_{i,r}$ = Total domestic private consumption of commodity i in destination r ; $QDG_{i,r}$ = Total domestic government consumption of commodity i in destination r ; $QF_{j,i,r}$ = Total intermediates of commodity i in sector j in destination r ; $QP_{i,r}$ = Total private consumption of commodity i in destination r ; $QG_{i,r}$ = Total government consumption of commodity i in destination r ;

Figure 18: The structure of international Trade in standard ICES

Final demand

The model considers a representative regional household, which allocates its income into three main components, namely private consumption, public consumption, and savings according to a Cobb-Douglas function. This means the three components are fixed shares (equal to the base year) of the disposable income level. The regional household holds income from capital, labour, land, and natural resources. Capital is mobile across sectors and while fixed in each time period it accumulates over time according to the recursive dynamics of the model. Aggregate private consumption is allocated among commodities following a Constant Difference Elasticity (CDE) utility function, while public consumption follows Cobb-Douglas utility function. Regional savings are private savings only and are collected by a Global bank which redistributes those resources as investments among regions according to GDP growth and the differentials in rates of return. The breakdown of investment into demand for final commodities is done using fixed shares, with changes in aggregate investment leading to proportional increases in the demand for individual commodities. Therefore, there is no real compositional shift in investment following changes in relative commodity prices.

System constraints and Macroeconomic closures

Equilibrium in the goods and services market is met when demand for commodities and services equals supply. Aggregate demand is composed of household and

government consumption spending, investment, exports, and transaction services demand. Supply includes both domestic production and imported commodities. Equilibrium is achieved through the endogenous interaction of domestic and foreign prices: shifts in relative prices have effects on sectoral production and sectoral primary factor uses, and hence institutional incomes and demand.

Both capital and labour are fully employed and perfectly mobile across sectors, implying that sector-specific returns adjust to ensure that demand for factors equals total supply.

The trade balance is endogenously determined and the difference between export and imports is equal to the gap between regional investment and savings.

Being based on the GTAP framework, ICES is a neoclassical model and as such it assumes that the savings level is most important when determining an economy's level of investment and output. This suggests that savings is exogenous, and that investment adjusts to maintain the savings-investment balance.

Appendix C. Shocks on land productivity

Figure 19. Percentage change in land productivity with respect to current climate in RCP2.6 by 2070

Figure 20. Percentage change in land productivity with respect to current climate in RCP6.0 by 2070

Appendix D. Climate change impacts on energy demand

Figure 21. Climate change impacts on electricity demand in RCP2.6 (above) and RCP6.0 (below) by 2070

Figure 22. Climate change impact on gas demand in RCP2.6 (above) and RCP6.0 (below) by 2070

Figure 23. Climate change impacts on oil product demand in RCP2.6 (above) and RCP6.0 (below) by 2070

Appendix E. Additional figures and results for 2030

Figure 24. Relative comparative advantage, share of exports over production and production of agricultural sectors in European regions in 2030

Figure 25 Sectoral production, exports and RCA for the Food industry in European regions in 2030

Figure 26. Climate change impacts of agriculture. RCA and Exports in 2030 (% change wrt baseline)

Figure 27. Climate change impacts of agriculture on trade and competitiveness of the EU food industry in 2030.

Figure 28. Relative comparative advantage, share of exports over production and production of energy and EITE sectors in European regions in 2030

Figure 29. Climate change impacts on energy demand: RCA and exports of energy and EITE sectors in EU regions in 2030 (% change wrt baseline)

Figure 30. Sectoral production, exports and RCA for macro sectors in European regions by 2030

Figure 31. Climate change impacts on energy demand: RCA and exports of macro sectors in EU regions in 2030 (% change wrt baseline)

Appendix F. Additional figures and results for 2070

Figure 32. Relative comparative advantage, share of exports over production and production of agricultural sectors in European regions in 2070

Figure 33. Sectoral production, exports and RCA for the food industry in European regions in 2070

Figure 34. Climate change impacts of agriculture. RCA and Exports in 2070 (% change wrt baseline)

Figure 35. Climate change impacts of agriculture on trade and competitiveness of the EU food industry in 2070

Figure 36. Relative comparative advantage, share of exports over production and production of energy and EITE sectors in European regions in 2070

Figure 37. Sectoral production, exports and RCA for macro sectors in European regions by 2070

Figure 38. Climate change impacts on energy demand: RCA and exports of macro sectors in EU regions in 2070 (% change wrt baseline)

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